

Mbuti

also known as “BaMbuti”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: African Religions, Religious Group

The Mbuti are a traditionally hunting and gathering-based society located in the Ituri Forest of what is now the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The Mbuti are also typically divided by hunting method: some bands use archery for hunting, while others use a net-hunting method (Beierle, 1995:1). This entry focuses on the net-hunting Mbuti located near the village of Epulu in 1950. At this time, the region had been under Belgian control for over 70 years. However, most cultural contact occurred with the neighboring Bantu villages, many of whose traits (including language and circumcision) the Mbuti adopted. Mbuti religion centers around the relationship of the society to the forest, which is understood to be sacred and to protect the Mbuti. The deity worshiped by the Mbuti (referred to by many different names) is simultaneously benevolent and a god of death, and is, by some understandings, the forest itself. A ceremony called the molimo is undertaken at various crises, during which songs are sung and noise is made to “wake up” the forest. Satani, tricky and clever spirits that were once people, are also important in Mbuti religion, and especially in the improvisatory legends (Beierle, 1995:5). For the Mbuti, religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1935 CE - 1960 CE

Region: Epulu Net hunters of Ituri Forest, ca. 1950

Region tags: Democratic Republic of the Congo

Epulu Net hunters of Ituri Forest, Democratic Republic of the Congo, ca. 1950

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, George P. 1962-1971. *Ethnographic Atlas*. *Ethnology* 1-10.
- Source 3: Murdock, George P., and Suzanne F. Wilson. 1972. "Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-cultural codes 3." *Ethnology* 11(3): 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fo04-001>

– Source 1 Description: Turnbull, Colin M. 1965a. "The Mbuti Pygmies: An Ethnographic Survey." In *Anthropological Papers*, 139-282, plates. New York: American Museum of Natural History.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fo04-002>

– Source 2 Description: Turnbull, Colin M. 1965b. *Wayward Servants: The Two Worlds of the African Pygmies*. Garden City, N.Y.: The Natural History Press.

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fo04-000>

– Source 1 Description: Beierle, John. 1995. "Culture Summary: Mbuti." New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

– Source 2 URL: <https://d-place.org/>

– Source 2 Description: Kirby, Kathryn R., Russell D. Gray, Simon J. Greenhill, Fiona M. Jordan, Stephanie Gomes-Ng, Hans-Jörg Bibiko, Damián E. Blasi, Carlos A. Botero, Claire Bowern, Carol R. Ember, Dan Leehr, Bobbi S. Low, Joe McCarter, William Divale, and Michael C. Gavin. 2016. D-PLACE: A Global Database of Cultural, Linguistic and Environmental Diversity. *PLoS ONE*, 11(7): e0158391. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0158391.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fo04-003>

– Source 3 Description: Turnbull, Colin M. 1962. *The Forest People*. New York, N.Y.: Simon and Schuster.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "At that mission prayers were said in public about five times a day, mention always being made of any converts who might be ill, however slightly. Prayers were also made requesting the Almighty to provide a road into the forest so that the mission could have easier access to the [Mbuti], and thanks were offered for a new automobile that had been acquired" (Turnbull, 1962:246).

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: "The relationship between the Mbuti and the villagers is maintained on several different levels, centering around trade. The [Mbuti] bring the villagers honey and meat in return for plantation products" (Beierle, 1995:3).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the absence of political and religious leaders: "Individual authority is unthinkable, and not only are there no chiefs or headmen in Mbuti society; there are not even any councils of elders or any ritual specialists such as prophets or diviners" (Turnbull, 1965b:181).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 40000

Notes: "From my own experience, and from discussion with missionaries and administrators who have attempted counts, one way or another, I would hazard a guess at somewhere around 40,000, with no evidence to show that the population is increasing, but certainly none to show that it is decreasing" (Turnbull, 1965b:26).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "Individual authority is unthinkable, and not only are there no chiefs or headmen in Mbuti society; there are not even any councils of elders or any ritual specialists such as prophets or diviners" (Turnbull, 1965b:181).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: ". . . it seems appropriate to mention the coincidence of two deficiencies--a lack of any real body of traditional folklore, on the one hand, and a lack of traditional magical belief and practice, on the other" (Turnbull, 1965a:270d).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972, Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures), "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (pgs. 259, 266; note: equivalent to SCCS variable 66).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "There are no bachelor huts or huts for unmarried girls or widows, and no ritual structures" (Turnbull, 1965a:195a).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . all songs are sacred as all are related to forest activities and the forest itself is sacred" (Turnbull, 1965a:234c).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: ". . . all songs are sacred as all are related to forest activities and the forest itself is sacred" (Turnbull, 1965a:234c).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "There is some indication . . . that the net hunters believe that when a body dies, a vital part of it, the personality or soul, leaves. It may become either a forest sprite (satani), or it may go to some other place where it will have nothing further to do with the living" (Turnbull, 1965a:238b).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "There is hardly any information on the notions of the net hunters on life after death, except that they firmly believe that life continues in some form or another, in much the same way that it is lived by the living" (Turnbull, 1965a:238b).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Burial is the custom among the net hunters, as with the archers" (Turnbull, 1965a:222b).

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Burial is the custom among the net hunters, as with the archers" (Turnbull, 1965a:222b).

Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: "No weapons, utensils, ornaments, or food are buried with the corpse" (Turnbull, 1965a:222b).

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that huts are demolished in order to cover the grave, and the surrounding area subsequently abandoned: "In general [burial] follows the same pattern [for Epulu net hunters as for archers], taking place inside or immediately beside the [hut] of the deceased; the [hut] is pulled down over the grave and the camp deserted immediately" (Turnbull, 1965a:222b).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a supreme high god, previously human spirits, and non-human supernatural beings. See questions below for details.

A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "Absent or not reported" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

– Yes

Notes: "The names given to the divinity are Mu(n)gu, Keti, Kalisia, and So(n)ge. Epulu net hunters also loosely use the term Mungu, as do the neighboring [Bira] villagers" (Turnbull,

1965a:236c).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

Notes: "... abnormal conditions of the physical world denote the presence of the chthonic God" (Turnbull, 1965a:237b).

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: While ethnographic evidence indicates that the high god does not have a connection to the elder in a lineage, evidence indicates a belief that the high god is primarily concerned with one's own group: "There is no evidence of any connection between God and the lineage through the elder, but each hunting band seems to regard Mungu, while God of all Mbuti every where, as being particularly concerned with them" (Turnbull, 1965a:237b).

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: "Among the Efulu net hunters, Kalisia [a different supreme high god] is apparently unknown to the Mbuti, who use the term Mungu both among themselves and when talking with villagers. This God is benevolent, though in some mysterious way that does not detract from his benevolence he is associated with death" (Turnbull, 1965a:237a).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "... abnormal conditions of the physical world denote the presence of the chthonic God. At such times the net hunters are careful not to expose themselves to his sight, which would bring death, nor to attract his attention by unseemly behavior" (Turnbull, 1965a:237b).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "There is some indication . . . that the net hunters believe that when a body dies, a vital part of it, the personality or soul, leaves. It may become either a forest sprite (satani), or it may go to some other place where it will have nothing further to do with the living" (Turnbull, 1965a:238b).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Disaster, ill fortune, and lack of success in the chase are usually attributed to satani (also sitani, shaitani) . . ." (Turnbull, 1965a:237a).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The net hunters have a particular fear of water and, as do the local villagers, seem to believe in water spirits, or, as they call them, 'water animals'" (Turnbull, 1965a:237b).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a supreme high god, previously human spirits, and non-human supernatural beings. See Turnbull, 1965a:236-238 for more information.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In the forest they feel and observe a certain restraint. Their songs are related to and emphasize their supreme value--the forest. Their daily activities are dominated by the forest and the hunt and the need for close cooperation. Once in the village, however, forest values are cast off" (Turnbull, 1965a:259a-259b).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that social norms are context dependent: "In the forest they feel and observe a certain restraint. Their songs are related to and emphasize their supreme value--the forest. Their daily activities are dominated by the forest and the hunt and the need for close cooperation. Once in the village, however, forest values are cast off" (Turnbull, 1965a:259a-259b).

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: "In the forest they feel and observe a certain restraint. Their songs are related to and emphasize their supreme value--the forest. Their daily activities are dominated by the forest and the hunt and the need for close cooperation. Once in the village, however, forest values are cast off" (Turnbull, 1965a:259a-259b).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Even a brief glance at the legends reveals that the one quality to which these Mbuti attach the greatest importance is cleverness . . . the sin of sins is stupidity." (Turnbull, 1965a:263d).

Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: "Even a brief glance at the legends reveals that the one quality to which these Mbuti attach the greatest importance is cleverness . . . the sin of sins is stupidity." (Turnbull, 1965a:263d).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: ". . . both premarital and postmarital sexual relations among the net hunters seem equally open, if not quite equally free" (Turnbull, 1965a:221c).

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: ". . . both premarital and postmarital sexual relations among the net hunters seem equally open, if not quite equally free" (Turnbull, 1965a:221c).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "The totem [animal or plant] is always taboo for the Mbuti. One may never eat it, and often not kill it, touch it, or even eat the food normally eaten by the totemic species. Breach of taboo is believed to involve serious illness or death" (Turnbull, 1965a:192a).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: "Cicatrization is very rare" (Turnbull, 1965a:168b).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: "I have met net hunters who stoutly deny that they would waste food in this way [through sacrifice]; certainly I never saw any offerings being made" (Turnbull, 1965a:237d).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "But Putnam [ethnographer who studied the Epuhu Net hunters] disagrees strongly that prayer or invocation is involved [in religious practice]" (Turnbull, 1965a:237d).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that small-scale rituals are present but not required: "Individuals may and do indulge in the spontaneous practice of sympathetic magic, but this is informal and unsystematized" (Turnbull, 1965a:256d).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The molimo ceremony is performed primarily by men and is associated with singing and the use of a particular type of horn, called the molimo horn. The molimo is particularly associated with

death, but it may be performed at any crisis, such as a poor hunting season" (Beierle, 1995:4). Ethnographic evidence indicates that the molimo ceremony is performed by the Epulu Net hunters: "For the net hunters, the molimo is their only means of dealing with the unknown, with situations for which they have no practical, immediately effective remedy" (Turnbull, 1965a:256d).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple extra-ritual in-group markers, including tattoos, food taboos, shaved heads, hats and headdresses, ornamentation, plucked eyelashes, chipped teeth, and body paint. See questions below for details.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "Men may tattoo their foreheads; women, their faces, stomachs, and backs" (Turnbull, 1965a:168b).

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that circumcision was present at the time focus of this entry, but was only performed with other religious groups: "Circumcision above all is a villager custom and has nothing to do with Mbuti initiation" (Turnbull, 1965a:184b).

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "The totem [animal or plant] is always taboo for the Mbuti. One may never eat it, and often not kill it, touch it, or even eat the food normally eaten by the totemic species. Breach of taboo is believed to involve serious illness or death" (Turnbull, 1965a:192a).

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: "Schebesta mentions as a peculiar 'Bambuti' custom the plucking of eyelashes, also the shaving of the head for esthetic effect" (Turnbull, 1965a:168b). Additionally: "Sometimes even head shaving is performed in such a way as to leave simple designs" (Turnbull, 1965a:233d).

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: "A variety of hats and headdresses is used by the net hunters . . ." (Turnbull, 1965a:200b).

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "A variety of hats and headdresses is used by the net hunters, also bracelets, necklaces, combs, and lip plugs" (Turnbull, 1965a:200b).

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Plucked eyelashes

Notes: "Schebesta mentions as a peculiar 'Bambuti' custom the plucking of eyelashes . . ." (Turnbull, 1965a:168b).

– Yes [specify]: Chipped teeth

Notes: "Teeth may be chipped . . ." (Turnbull, 1965a:168b).

– Yes [specify]: Body paint

Notes: "All Mbuti . . . like to paint the body for esthetic effect as opposed to the magical significance of facial painting. White, red, and black are the colors used, the dyes being obtained from clay and certain barks" (Turnbull, 1965a:168b-169a).

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: "As may be seen in the survey, however, there is one striking difference between the account by Putnam and that by Schebesta, and that is the lack in Putnam's description of any institution such as karé brotherhood [an institution that forms fictive kin ties between adult men]" (Turnbull, 1965a:252b).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, the Mbuti have no jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32). Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicate that the Mbuti have bilateral descent without kindreds. Additionally, the Mbuti live in agamous communities without localized clans, lineal kin groups, or exogamy (Murdock, 1962-1971, columns 19, 20, 22). Information on jurisdictional hierarchy and kin ties indicate that the Mbuti are most accurately characterized as a band.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that famine is absent: "Although their time is fully occupied by the requirements of their hunting and gathering existence, the Mbuti never have any fear of shortage and consequently have no need to store" (Turnbull, 1965a:165d).

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that famine is absent: "Although their time is fully occupied by the requirements of their hunting and gathering existence, the Mbuti never have any fear of shortage and consequently have no need to store" (Turnbull, 1965a:165d).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: "There is no record of any form of execution, though it has been known for the aged and infirm, too sick to care for themselves, or for those suspected of being possessed of supernatural powers, to disappear or to die of some strange sickness, under unusual circumstances" (Turnbull, 1965a:231d).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, the Mbuti do not utilize food storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, the Mbuti do not utilize food storage (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Taxation

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: "... villagers were taxed by the [Belgian] administration and exemption was granted to all Mbuti ..." (Turnbull, 1965a:274b).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, police functions are not specialized (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: "He [an informant] was forced into admitting that he did not consider the [Mbuti] real people, and therefore they had no right to have cases tried in the tribunal" (Turnbull, 1962:234).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that punishment is not institutionalized: "Petty pilfering is considered as theft, and theft is both forbidden and punished; but Schebesta does not describe any system of punishment" (Turnbull, 1965a:186b).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Mbuti may have been subject to the legal code of the neighboring Bira villages: "Although essentially an individual relationship rather than a band relationship, failure on the part of an Mbuti to respond to his karé is considered by the villagers as a violation of village law, and can be made into a lineage/lineage or a band/village issue, but with predictable lack of success because of the absence of any effective agency of control" (Turnbull, 1965b:227).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 [of Cultural Complexity] - Writing and Records, the Mbuti do not possess a distinct written language (Murdock and Provost, 1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Mbuti depend primarily on hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting), with gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: The Mbuti depend primarily on hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting), with gathering (SCCS Variable 203, Dependence on Gathering) as a secondary means of subsistence (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 7).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The relationship between the Mbuti and the villagers is maintained on several different levels, centering around trade. The [Mbuti] bring the villagers honey and meat in return for plantation products" (Beierle, 1995:3).

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Mbuti are in contact with Bira villagers: "Schebesta's division of the Ituri Mbuti into Aka, Efe, and Sua [Epulu Net hunters] is a linguistic classification and, at that, a division not according to Mbuti languages but to the villager linguistic groups--Mangbetu, Lese, and Bira, respectively" (Turnbull, 1965a:154b). According to Ethnographic Atlas column 28, Intensity of Cultivation, the Bira rely primarily on small-scale agriculture (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from D-PLACE, Kirby et al., 2016).